

APPLICATION TO GRAPHITE EPOXY STRUT FOR EFFU STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Study on graphite epoxy struts as a light weight structural element had started in 1987. The strut was applied to the structure of Exposed Facility Flyer Unit (EFFU) based on results of the study. EFFU is installed on the Space Free-flyer Unit (SFU) that was recently launched by Japanese H-II rocket and will be retrieved by the Space Shuttle. The EFFU was developed in three steps. Element technology test was carried out to acquire mechanical property data for graphite epoxy strut element. And design allowable was determined based on test data. Engineering model test was performed to verify structural strength and stiffness for flight equivalent structure assembly. Protoflight model test was completed to confirm the performance of the flight article.

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on our study on the graphite epoxy struts as a light weight structural element, the struts were applied to main structure of Exposed Facility Flyer Unit (EFFU), cf. [1],[2]. In these days, graphite epoxy is popular material for space vehicle and satellites structures, but for main structure of Space Shuttle payload, it is the first application in Japan.

The EFFU is installed on SFU as a partial model of Japanese Experiment Module (JEM) Exposed Facility. SFU was launched by H-II rocket in 18th of March 1995, then various tests will be performed for 4.5 months on the orbit of 500 km altitude, and will be retrieved by US Space Shuttle and will return to the ground. The mission sequence is shown in figure 1. A fluid loop thermal control system, and equipment exchange unit on EFFU will work as the first experiments in Japan. Moreover, a chemical vapor deposition experiment device is also installed for operation, and it is expected that the results from this operation will be utilized for the Space Station or Space Platform. The configuration of SFU and EFFU are shown in figure 2.

2. OUTLINE OF EFFU STRUCTURE

The followings are major requirements for the EFFU structure:

- (1) Maximum dimension : 1.5m x 1.5m x 1.05m
- (2) Load condition : limit load = according to requirements of H-II rocket and Space Shuttle
ultimate load = 1.25 times of limit load for H-II rocket
1.4 times of limit load for the Shuttle

- (3) Stiffness (minimum frequency) : 40 Hz and above (longitudinal direction)
25 Hz and above (lateral direction)
with rigid constraint at SFU interface points.
- (4) Mass of load : 300 kg max. (including mass of structure)
- (5) Fracture control : To perform identification of fracture critical parts and analysis of safe life.
For composite/bonded structure : Adequate non destructive evaluation (NDE) and proof test requirement

The EFFU structure including graphite epoxy struts (T800)/epoxy) and a titanium (Ti-6Al-4V) alloy cross type beam are connected with bolts at each node. The primary structure consists of graphite epoxy struts (T800)/epoxy) and a titanium (Ti-6Al-4V) alloy cross type beam are connected with bolts at each node. Mass of the structure is about 80kg including secondary structures of equipment loading panel and radiator support frame. Proof test of 120% of the limit load is required for every graphite epoxy strut and non destructive test performed prior to and after the proof test.

(Note)
 Total mass: Approx. 4 t (Mission: App. 1 t)
 Power: Approx. 2 kW (Mission: App. 1 kW)
 SFU Dia: 4.5 m

Figure 1. Flight operation profile of SFU

Figure 2. SFU and EFFU

Figure 3. Configuration of EFFU structure

Figure 4. Graphite epoxy strut

3. NASA'S REQUIREMENTS FOR COMPOSITE / BONDED STRUCTURES

Structural requirements for space shuttle payloads are specified in NASA's documents of NSTS 14046B: "Payload Structural Verification Requirements" and NHB 8071.1A: "Fracture Control Requirements for using the National Space Transportation System". Those includes special requirements for composite / bonded structures as follows:

- (1) To use only manufacturing processes and controls that are demonstrated to be reliable and consistent with established aerospace industries practice.
- (2) Material design properties must comply with MIL-HDBK-17 allowable, or manufactures minimum guaranteed allowable or must be developed for specific manufacturing processes using a statistically valid data base that has prior approval the NSTS structural/mechanical

working group.

- (3) All composite/bonded structures deemed fracture critical shall be shown to meet fracture control requirements by one of two following methods:
 - a. A proof test to no less than 120 percent of the limit load. The proof test shall be conducted on the flight article.
 - b. A damage tolerance test program to establish that these structures possess at least four service lifetimes. These tests shall be conducted on full scale flight like elements of critical components and samples with controlled flaws or damage. The size and shape of the flaws or damage must be representative of those that could occur on the flight part.
- (4) For all fracture critical composite/bonded components, procedures for the prevention of damage resulting from handling or final assembly shall be addressed in the fracture control plan and approved by the responsible NASA center or sponsoring agency.

4. APPLICABILITY WITH NASA'S STRUCTURAL REQUIREMENTS

EFFU structure is developed in three phase, element technology test, engineering model test and protoflight model test. The compliance with above requirements was verified in combinations of those tests. In element technology test, coupons and graphite epoxy struts were tested to acquire basic data for safety requirements of NASA. And baseline of manufacturing procedure, non-destructive test, proof test and product assurance were established. In engineering model test, graphite epoxy struts were assembled in main truss of EFFU structure, after screening by proof test. Then, static load test and vibration test were carried out for structure assembly, and confirmed structural strength, and stiffness to withstand lift off and landing environments.

4.1 ELEMENT TECHNOLOGY TEST

Material test with the purpose of obtaining data for safety review of NASA performed for following items.

1. Verification of the strength of composite tubes and metal bonded parts, evaluation of stiffness and space environment resistivity.
2. Verification of strength of composite strut assemblies bonded to metal parts at each end of composite tubes and stiffness evaluation and verification of heat resistance to thermal cycle environment.
3. Acquisition of out gas property data for graphite epoxy.

Test pieces are shown in figure 5, and test flows of element technology test is shown in figure 6. Following results were obtained in element technology tests.

- (1) Design allowable for strength and modulus were obtained based on test data of graphite epoxy test pieces as equivalent B-basis value of MIL-HDBK-5E.
- (2) Design allowable for shear strength at bonded joints were obtained based on test data of double lap shear test pieces as equivalent B-basis value of MIL-HDBK-5E.
- (3) Bond strength between composite tube and metal parts dominate strength of struts.
- (4) Strength data of bonded joint is shown in figure 7.

From above test results, we established equivalent B-basis value of distribution for strength of bonded joint as design allowable. And,

- (5) We established test method of ultrasonic inspection of the bonded part of struts, and we obtained reproducible data for NDE by using same master piece.
- (6) Electron beam irradiation and thermal cycle exposure caused no degradation in strength and stiffness.

Furthermore, we assembled struts into truss type partial structure model, and applied static load at limit and ultimate levels two directions. The test results showed that the partial structure model had

sufficient strength and stiffness. Test article is shown in figure 8.

Figure 5. Test pieces for element technology test

Figure 6. Flow of element technology test

Table 1. Summary of element technology test result

	Test Description	Test Result
Coupon	Static Load	Modulus : 108 GPa (equivalent B-basis value) Strength : 1470 MPa (equivalent B-basis value)
	Electron Beam irradiation	Less degradation of strength and stiffness by 1.2 Mrad (1.2 Mrad = irradiation for 12 years on altitude earth orbit)
	Thermal Cycle	Less degradation of strength and stiffness by thermal cycles of - 30 to 60 °C / 80 cycles
	Out gas	Total Mass Loss : 0.667% (< 1% : NASA recommendation) Volatile condensable mass : 0.000% (< 0.1% : ditto)
Struts	Static Load	Modulus : 85.32 GPa (equivalent B-basis value) Strength : 46.1 kN (equivalent B-basis value)
	Thermal Cycle	Less degradation of strength and stiffness by thermal cycles of - 30 to 60 °C / 80 cycles

Figure 7. Strength test result for graphite epoxy strut

Figure 8. Partial structure model for element technology test

4.2 ENGINEERING MODEL(EM) TEST

Structural development model(SDM) was manufactured and tested to verify the applicability to structural requirements.

Ultrasonic inspection (UT) and proof test were carried out for all struts of the model. Protection covers from impact damage were applied. Manufacturing flow is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9. Manufacturing process for graphite epoxy strut

4.3 CONFIRMATION TEST BEFORE MANUFACTURING PROTOFLIGHT MODEL

At NASA safety review phase 2, effect of temperature on bonding strength of graphite epoxy strut was pointed out. Then we acquired strength data under elevated temperature and low temperature. The effect of temperature on bonding strength is shown in figure 10. Shear strength at bonded joint is reduced at elevated temperature (near curing temperature) than room temperature (as bonding temperature). It means that bonding strength of adhesive is reduced at elevated temperature, and thermal stress between titanium end metal and graphite epoxy tube is proportional to difference from room temperature. Then, it is concluded that strength of the struts is reduced at elevated temperature because of the summation of reduced adhesive strength and increased thermal stress, and the proof test shall be conducted under elevated temperature (60°C).

Figure 10. Effect of temperature on bonding strength

4.4 PROTOFLIGHT MODEL (PFM) TEST

For protoflight model, proof test was conducted for all graphite epoxy struts in 60 °C, and static load test was carried out to confirm appropriateness as a flight structure.

5. SUMMARY OF VERIFICATION RESULTS FOR NASA FRACTURE CONTROL REQUIREMENTS

Verification results for NASA fracture control requirements are summarized in table 1. Design and verification approach of the graphite epoxy strut was admitted at safety review phase 2 of NASA in September 1991. Furthermore April in 1994, verification results were also admitted at safety review phase 3.

Table 1. NASA structural requirements and verification status

Requirements	Verification Results	Element	EM	PFM
3.2 (1) Requirements for manufacturing processes and controls	1. To manufacture under control of contractor's quality assurance system that meet NASDA's requirements. 2. Basically same manufacturing process for EM and PFM that was established by element tech. test.	Done	Done Done	Done Done
3.2 (2) Requirements for material design properties	1. To use B-basis allowable developed by our strut data base obtained by element tech. test, with statistically valid. 2. To evaluate environment effects(thermal cycle, electron beam, out gas) on allowable using coupon and strut test data.	Done Done		
3.2 (3) Requirements for fracture critical composite/bonded components	1. To conduct the required proof test (120% of limit load) at the strut level for all struts. 2. To conduct ultrasonic inspection before and after proof test.	Done Done	Done Done	Done Done
3.2 (4) Requirements for prevention of damage for fracture critical composite/bonded components	1. To require the protection in the process. (strut level: container, assembly level : bubble sheet)		Done	Done

6. CONCLUSION

SFU was launched by H-II rocket successfully in 18th of march this year, and EFFU graphite epoxy struts will become the flight proven structure after retrieval this winter. It will also prove our structural verification activities to the NASA's requirements was proper. We hope the results shown in this paper will be some guideline of the composite / bonded structure development as a shuttle payload structure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was under contract of National Space Development Agency of Japan (NASDA).

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